

IMPROVING THE PRIORITY FACTORS ASSESSMENT SYSTEM OF THE TERRITORIAL DEVELOPMENT OF LIGHT INDUSTRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10065859>

Abstract

In this article, priority factors with a high level of influence of the factor remain or increase are divided into the "Hard" group, and the factors whose decrease is observed are divided into the "Soft" group.

Key words: investment potential, level of employment, gender indicator of employment, foreign trade relations and status, technical possibilities of production, conditions of innovative development, demography of enterprises, "Hard" group and "Soft" group factors.

Light industry plays a crucial role in the modern economy by producing consumer goods that are generally smaller in size and require less capital investment than heavy industry.

In general, the importance of the light industrial sector lies in its ability to stimulate economic growth, create jobs, support innovation, contribute to regional development and environmental sustainability.

Territorial development of the light industry network depends on a number of factors, such as the ecological environment, infrastructure, natural location, socio-economic potential of the region, including specialization in industrial production, investment attractiveness, entrepreneurial ability of the population, culture, traditions, intellectual reserve and outlook. will depend.

A number of factors are discussed in the sources about the wide class of factors affecting regional development. According to it, the investment potential and investment attractiveness of the region, the level of employment, the gender indicator of employment, clustering of production enterprises, foreign trade relations and status, technical possibilities of production, conditions for innovative development, demography of enterprises, the level of development of other economic sectors, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, the standard of living of the population, the material and financial provision of jobs in the industry, the intellectual potential of enterprises and the ability to create additional value, environmental relations and the status of the implementation of the green economy system in the region were highlighted as priority aspects.

The reasons for the priority of these factors in the development of light industry are explained by their importance in quantitatively increasing the volume of production, qualitatively, in ensuring optimal management and efficiency of organizational mechanisms. In our opinion, while any priority factor has the above qualities, it is important to pay attention to the conditions, condition, and permeability of the development environment of the network. Otherwise, the primary conclusions will remain significant only according to their theoretical essence. Therefore, in order for the priority factors to maintain their status, it is necessary to check to what extent the highly rated impact level is absorbed into the network environment, and to evaluate how the development process under the influence of the factor considered as a priority reacts to the source of the same factor. Here, the level of influence of the accepted factor on the network environment may weaken, remain unchanged or increase due to the opposition of uncertain socio-economic or other laws in the development processes of the network. As a result, a group of influencing factors is formed. We suggest to divide the priority factors whose high influence level of the factor remains or increases into the "Hard" group, and the factors whose decrease is observed into the "Soft" group. As a result, it becomes possible to give a new feature to any priority factors and differentiate them positionally.

One of the main factors stimulating the increase in the volume of light industry is the export potential of the sector. Increasing the share of export products in the volume of products produced in the network by 1% leads to an increase in production volume by 2.38%. It follows that one of the priority directions of development of the industry is to turn it into an export-oriented industry.

The increase in the number of jobs in the light industry network is a factor that is quickly accepted into the network environment, a necessary aspect in development. In fact, reducing the number of workers in the production process does not increase the volume of production.

Production of exportable products is one of the main tasks in the activity of light industrial enterprises. In the future, the number of light industrial enterprises among export-oriented enterprises, the share of branch products in the export composition of the region, and the importance of the region's export potential are expected to increase. Because the export potential of the industry is evaluated as a factor that is quickly accepted by the development environment.

Carrying out small business and private entrepreneurship activities in the light industry network will become one of the promising directions. The growth of the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the production of light industry is evaluated by the development environment of the network as a factor that is quickly accepted. and other possibilities can be explained.

The priority factors related to the "Soft" group include the amount of investments in the network, the increase in the number of clustered light industrial enterprises, innovative development, the share of women in the number of jobs in the network, the level of technical modernization of light industrial enterprises, import costs, the number of light industrial enterprises that have been terminated, cotton fiber production, In light industry, ecological index factors are compatible.

Summary

The volume of investments in the network is related to the main resource supply. The offer of investors can greatly influence the direction of development of the network. It is known that the effectiveness of the development direction can increase gradually. This process is measured in "big" numbers in terms of time.

The increase in the number of clustered light industrial enterprises is characterized by the fact that the operating entities do not correspond to the management and development plans developed for many years. The level of innovative development of enterprises is accompanied by an increase in the efficiency of the use of intellectual resources in their activities, and the introduction of advanced foreign experience. This requires enterprises to evaluate the existing potential, improve the mechanisms of their use, and create conditions.

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